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Tourism Innovations is a Journal of Indian Tourism and Hospitality Congress (ITHC). It is a bi-annual international referred research Journal focusing on academic perspectives in Tourism and Hospitality. Being an journal of inter-disciplinary field, the journal focuses on various aspects of tourism and hospitality like, Tourism Issues, Tourism Impacts, Eco-tourism, Sustainable Tourism, Tourism Marketing, Medical Tourism, Health Tourism, Culture Tourism, Culinary Arts, Service Operations and other tourism, travel and hospitality areas. The objective of the journal is to have a comprehensive collection of research articles and dispersal of updated knowledge and information about tourism sector.

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Abstract

Over tourism is the perceived congestion or overcrowding from an excess of tourists, resulting in conflicts with locals. The term has only been used frequently since 2012, but is now the most commonly used expression to describe the negative impacts ascribed to tourism. The growth of tourism can lead to conflicts over the use of space between residents, commuters, day-visitors and overnight tourists. Although much attention is currently given to over tourism in cities, it can also be observed in rural destinations, or on islands. Several media outlets have published lists of destinations that are not recommended because of an excessive number of tourists. Over tourism is related to the terms carrying capacity, which describes a maximum number of tourists that a destination can host and overcrowding, which describes a situation where too many people visit a specific place for safety or comfort reasons. Particularly in city destinations, the number of residents and commuters has risen rapidly in recent years, which has led to increased pressure on infrastructure and facilities and a heightened sense of crowdedness.

Overtourism – A Blight to Sustainability: Case Study of Shimla**Dr. Sandeep Guleria**

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1. Introduction

The word Overtourism has become the point of concern these days in tourism industry. It is defined as overcrowding by excess of tourist at a given place resulting in conflicts with locals. The term Overtourism or Mass tourism has been the term for concern and discussion in tourism industry. Still, it seems to remain an 'ambiguous' term, lacking clear viewpoint for the definition (Torres, 2002), may be due to its multidimensional character that evokes different meanings for different people (Miller and Auyong, 1998), and overall, the nature of tourism is multifaceted (Pearce, 1992). The growth in tourism sector can cause the overtourism at given place as same is to be used by tourists, commuters and local community. It has been known that tourism demand and supply have become more independent, individual, flexible and active (e.g. Boissevain, 1996; Ioannides and Debbage, 1998; Kontogeorgopoulos, 2004; Poon, 1993; Swarbrooke and Horner, 2007; Torres, 2002), which is understood either as the end of mass tourism (e.g. Poon, 1993) or its development into different forms (e.g. Ioannides and Debbage, 1998; Torres, 2002). These different interpretations suggest that the term mass tourism or over tourism should be critically examined. To have the relevance of different other forms of tourism the term overtourism need to be defined and explained carefully. One of the good examples of is the case of comparison between mass, alternative and ecotourism. Where Ecotourism has

been identified as opposite to mass tourism (Walpole and Goodwin, 2000) but also as its variant (Weaver, 2001), or the separation between them is seen as blurred (Collins-Kreiner and Israeli, 2010). As for India is concerned it should not be an issue, as with a population of 1.3 billion the no. of foreign tourist arrival is just 10 million approximately per year. Whereas it is 38 million to the country like Thailand with total population of 69 million only. There are many destinations in India which are not recommended to be visited by the travel experts due to overtourism and are overcrowded by tourists and most of the part of the nation is still to receive numbers of foreign tourists. Basically what our Indian tourism Industry need to develop new niche for tourism and learn crowd management. Many sites which are frequented by domestic tourists require more attention toward crowd management. Best examples can be seen as long queues in front of any religious destination be it Tirupathi or Sai Temple at shirdi. Not only the popular sites visited by mass tourists, but it has started affecting the alternate sectors tourism industry as well. In adventure tourism there are certain treks and trails which have become the modernised tent jungle. One of the reasons for that may be mushrooming of unlicensed adventure tour operator in the region which is hampering the sustainability.

1.1 Development of Overtourism

Increase in number of host population and commuters: In recent past, the growth of number of residents and commuters particularly in cities has risen sharply. Which ultimately exert more pressure on resources and spread more crowdedness.

Changing lifestyles: The increase in disposable income and changing lifestyle patterns of the residents lead to a monoculture of hospitality facilities which ultimately tends to share the common sphere by residents and visitors.

Social media: This platform has played major role for overtourism over the years. Experiences are shared on social media which ultimately lead to overcrowding of the place which is shared and have received more likes.

1.2 Measures against Overtourism

In September 2013, the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) published a report

on overtourism and how to deal with it. It highlights the importance of looking at tourism in a local context and details strategies to deal with overtourism:

Promote lesser unknown routes and attractions in a given destination

- Use regulations including restrictions on numbers of visitors within a certain time frame
- Improve guest segmentation
- Ensure local tourism benefits, especially through skilled jobs and participation of locals in tourism development
- Infrastructures with experience qualities for guests and population offer
- Public infrastructures, especially in transport, continue to improve
- Take local stakeholders seriously and involve them
- Inform and sensitize guests regarding local rules and values
- Use control and exchange mechanisms based on secure data and new technologies.

In the present chapter the case study of Shimla has been discussed which is about to pay price for overtourism in coming years if certain preventive measures would not been taken by policy makers. Shimla "Jewel of the Crown" (Pubby Vipin, 1996) is one of the most favourite place of Britishers for which they declared it as summer capital of India during British Raj. It is famous for its scenic beauty, pleasant weather during summers and heritage buildings. It is one of the most favourite places of North India for foreign visitors. But nowadays face of Shimla which once was known as queen of hills, is over exposed and has become very congested. Due to heavy rush in traffic, deforestation, pollution the quality of the air has been degraded. There are also many other problems which are faced by not only the tourists but local community also. The most common problems are monkey menace, water scarcity, parking, waste disposal etc. In nutshell the "queen of hills" has become the jungle of concrete. This chapter cater the study of environmental and infrastructural problems of the town related with overtourism. Both primary and secondary data has been used in the study.

2. Study Area

One of the lovely hill stations of North India, Shimla, a capital city is located in the middle ranges of Himalayas in the state of Himachal Pradesh with average altitude of 2100 meters above sea level. It is also one of the 12 districts of HP which is bounded by the state of Uttarakhand in the south-east, districts of Mandi and Kullu in the north, Kinnaur in the east, Sirmour in the south and Solan in the west. According to 2011 census, it has population of 169,578 with 93,152 males and 76,426 females. Major religion is Hinduism with 93.5% population followed by Islam 2.29%, Sikhism 1.95%, Buddhism 1.33%, Christianity 0.62% and Jainism 0.10%.

2.1 Main Attractions of Shimla

There are number of places for tourists to visit in Shimla most common are like the Mall, The Ridge, Lakkar Bazaar etc. Among the heritage buildings available in Shimla are Viceregal Lodge also known as Indian Institute of Advanced Studies, Kufri, Jakhoo hills, Christ Church, Annadale, Summer Hill, Chadwick Waterfall, State Museum, Kali Bari Temple, Gaeity Heritage Complex, Gorton Castle, Bantony Castle, Baba Bhalku Railway Museum, Sankat Mochan, Scandal Point, Naldehra, Rothery Castle, Mashobra, Fagu etc.

3. Study Design

To get the bird view of the implications of overtourism in Shimla, a survey has been conducted on Tourists, local community and service providers (Hoteliers and Travel Agents). Main problems which are being faced besides overtourism has been asked and those are affecting tourism in Shimla directly or indirectly. To avoid homogeneity samples has been taken from different parts of the town.

3.1 Demographic Profile of Tourists

Among domestic and foreign tourists, total 153 tourists have been surveyed from different parts of Shimla like Advanced Studies, The Mall, Lakkar Bazaar, Jakhoo, Tara Devi, Summer Hill, Kufri, Kali Bari etc. Among demographic profile, place of origin, gender, age, marital status, education, occupation, income etc have been asked. Besides demographic profile their travel

pattern and travel behaviour has also been taken into consideration by asking their decision of visiting Shimla, leisure activities they took part in Shimla, their satisfaction level regarding the services being provided in Shimla etc. Among all 63.52% were male and 46.48% were female. Data of 33.14% foreign and 66.86% domestic tourists has been surveyed. Majority of domestic tourists were from Punjab, Haryana, Delhi and some of them were from UP, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal, Rajasthan and Gujrat. Among foreign respondents most of them were from Israel, Germany, UK, Lebanon, Ukraine and Spain. From the educational profile the quality of data has been assessed only 12.14% respondents were below graduation, about 67.14% were graduates and rest of them possessed Post graduation or higher degree.

3.2 Profile of Service Providers

The travel agents and hoteliers are the one who are directly engaged in tourism related activities in Shimla. They are the one who have been witnessing the changing face of tourism in Shimla over the years. They are the one who are directly or indirectly affected due to problems generated by overtourism besides local community and tourists of course. Majorly budget class hotels and travel agencies at Mall road, Lakkar Bazaar and Sanjauli have been surveyed. They were asked about basic information facilities they are providing, number of years they are in tourism business and mainly problems faced by them over the years due to overtourism or any other issue. Total 20 travel agents and 33 budget class hotels have been surveyed. One of the questions asked from service providers was is there any conflict they have encountered due to overtourism with tourist. Only 7% responded no and 93% responded yes. Apart from problems related to tourists they shared their own problems as well. For example one of the major concern of all the hoteliers in Shimla is scarcity of water and second is parking. Other problems like traffic jams, space constraint, deforestation and other environmental factors were shared.

3.3 Perspective of host community

As overtourism is seen as one of the major reason for most of the problems be it traffic jam or scarcity of water. The perception of the local community is also very important

for any measure to be taken by the policy makers. Around 71 local people including teachers, shopkeepers, porters, drivers have been approached and surveyed from Summer hill, Boileuganj, Tutoo, Jatogh, Sanjauli and Vikasnagar.

4. Main Findings

After assessing the secondary and primary data collected from the responses of the Tourists, Service providers and Host community it has been found that to some extent overtourism plays a destructive role for sustainability in Shimla. Some of the main problems which are being faced by host community as well as visitors and service providers are given below:

1. Highly mismanaged traffic jams, although administration is playing their role judiciously, but due to rise in the number of taxis and private vehicles of tourist from outside slow downs the pace on almost all the roads linked to main city. The worst time is between 9 am to 11 am and then between 4 pm to 9 pm.
2. Other concern Parking for the vehicles, most of the site seeing of Shimla lacks this facility due to which already specified parking lots in lower Shimla gets overburdened which leads to high parking charges as well. In that case tourists are forced to park their vehicle at the edge of the road which again causes traffic jams. Except some good hotels, most of the budget class hotels or guest houses do not have their own parking lot.
3. Poor public transport of Shimla force tourists to bring their own vehicle or higher private taxi which leads to congestion as road density of Shimla is very poor as compared to the other cities of the region like Chandigarh.
4. The summers in Shimla witnessed where host community themselves pleaded to tourists not to come Shimla due to scarcity of water. According to CAG report, between 2009 to 2014 the per capital average water supplied in Shimla was 110 litres against the prescribed limit of 135 litres. But this year it had fallen below 50 litres per capital per day with piped water being supplied once a week. The only water sources which cater Shimla are Dhalli Catchment Area, Chair Nallah, Nauti Khad, Cherot jagroti Nallah and Ashwani Khad. Situation gets worst when this scarce of water in summer is shared with excess of tourists staying in hotels. In summers not only host community but tourists also complain for scarcity of water.
5. Still during the summers to avoid scorching heat of the plains and insurgency in Kashmir, most of the tourists chose Shimla for vacations and about 95% high-end hotels in Shimla have been booked to full capacity. ATMs of most of the banks except on The Mall went out of cash.
6. For providing facilities to the tourists, in the name of infrastructural development Shimla witnessed deforestation and environmental degradation in past years. Due to which forests have been vanished in and around the town. This lead to monkey menace in Shimla. Anyone can witness dozens of Monkeys or Langurs roaming around in every part of the Shimla.
7. Other concern which arises due to overtourism is solid waste. This solid waste asre polluting the town badly. Being a plastic free area, wrappers of toffees, chocolates or other eatables should not be seen in open. Due to lack of space the present solid waste treatment plant at Darani Ka Bagicha at Lal Pani, Shimla is not sufficient for proper disposal. So MC Shimla is planning to shift its present Solid Waste Management Plant to Bhariyal at Tara Devi Totu bye pass road.
8. Over the years Shimla is being seen as destination with fresh and pleasant environment. Tourists use to come here with the perception of physical and mental rejuvenation But due to increase in number of tourists every year the carrying capacity of the town is at stake. Government has no option but to develop more infrastructure to cater the needs of the tourists as tourism is one of the major contributor in the economy of the state. This year four laning of NH 5 lead to land slides and many mishaps during monsoons.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

Shimla once known as queen of hills still bears same charm in the heart of tourist. This is the only reason the number of tourists visiting Shimla every year has been increasing. This is very good to some extent as far as economic growth of the state is concerned. But at the same time it also make policy makers as well as others a bit worried about the ill effects of overtourism in the town for sustainability. One of the most important things which we need to sustain for our next generation is its colonial heritage buildings. Which requires upliftment if we want to sustain them. The excessive pressure of the tourists and local community as well as administration on these buildings leads to their degradation to some extent. In case of Shimla Overtourism lead to urbanisation, where there was a little scope for it. Still there are some measures which could be taken or adopted for the benefit of local community, tourists and industry. It is advisable that before taking any necessary measure the sustainability of the region should be given top priority. Some of the suggestions are as under:

1. First and the foremost is the awareness about the sustainability development among host community, tourists, service providers and of course other stake holders. Among tourists this awareness can be spread during peak season and events which are majorly organised for the tourist for example summer festival, apple festival etc. For host community it can be shared by organizing special awareness programs in community centres, parks, shopping complex, schools, colleges or any other educational institutes even in offices and other work places. To encourage the service providers special sops to be given to them under some program of sustainability by local administration.
2. A group of educated unemployed youth could be selected and trained them to be excellent professional guides who can speak influent English and Hindi. Their services could be utilized by the tourists and other stake holders.
3. To save all heritage building some NGOs or participation of locals is very much important. Although Government is

trying its level best to protect them. But it will be sustained only if host population and tourist community both are engaged for the sustainability of these buildings.

4. One of the major cause of degraded quality of the air in hills is vehicular traffic. For host population, if people are encouraged to use local transport instead of their personal vehicles it will lead to decongestion in the roads and control pollution also. For that first we require very good road network and good public transport system. For tourists the green tax on the vehicles from outside the state or exemption of the tax to the CNG vehicles can also improve the quality of air in the town. For better air quality vehicles older than 15 years should be restricted and there should be check on the number of diesel vehicles entering Shimla everyday.
5. It has been observed over the years there is no scope of widening the road in main town of the Shimla. The only option left with us is one way traffic and restriction of any vehicle in small roads except ambulances.
6. Before every tourist season (assuming that the main tourist season starts sometime in March/April) the PWD and National Highways Department should be asked to rectify all road defects and each important road should be travel-worthy. Each Superintending Engineer should be held responsible for the maintenance of these roads.
7. Railways must be given a boost so that tourists can enjoy ride from plains to Shimla and avoid their own vehicle to bring with them. Frequency of Low cost airlines and helicopter services can also be increased during peak season.
8. Till date the main attraction of Shimla is The Ridge which houses water storage tank below it and had developed cracks and the other is The Mall road. It is not possible if a tourist has come to Shimla and does not visit these 2 places. So, there must be some more places to be developed in the outskirts of Shimla which attract the tourists and release the pressure on these 2 sites. Some amusement park or theme park can be one of the good options.

9. The State Government of Himachal Pradesh should encourage people's participation in promotion of rural tourism to take tourism to the remotest corner of the State and acquaint visitors with the rich cultural heritage, customs and traditions of the villages so that tourism could become a household affair and number of tourists throughout the state can be rationalised.
10. Although after the year 2000, Government has taken very good measures to prevent deforestation and promote afforestation. Almost 55% of area around Shimla is covered with forest. Due to which so many landslides have been prevented. Further to prevent more landslides it is advisable to grow more OAK trees wherever we get place in Shimla.
11. One of the main concerns highlighted by all stake holders is the concern about the water scarcity. It can be minimized by taking help of rain water harvesting concept. This concept has already been proven a boon for the places like Andaman and Nicobar Islands, remote villages of Andhra Pradesh and Telengana. Unlike these places Shimla receives rain water in abundance during monsoons. This potential can be utilised to solve water problem of Shimla. Other alternative is to fetch water from the nearby perennial tributaries or Pabbar and Giri River.
12. All Centrally Sponsored Schemes under the Ministries of Tourism, Surface Transport, Health, Water Resources, Rural Development, Forests should be collectively tapped for promoting sustainability in the Shimla.

References

- Boissevain, J. (1996). 'Introduction', pp. 1-26 in J. Boissevain (ed.) *Coping with Tourists. Providence, RI: Berghahn Books.*
- Collins-Kreiner, N. and Y. Israeli (2010). 'Supporting an Integrated Soft Approach to Ecotourism Development: The Agmon Lake, Israel', *Tourism Geographies* 12(1): 118-39.
- Kontogeorgopoulos, N. (2004). 'Ecotourism and Mass Tourism in Southern Thailand: Spatial Interdependence, Structural Connections, and Staged Authenticity', *GeoJournal* 61(1): 1-11.
- Miller, M. L. and J. Auyong (1998). 'Remarks on Tourism Terminologies: Anti-Tourism, Mass Tourism, and Alternative Tourism', pp. 1-24 in M. L. Miller and J. Auyong (eds) *Proceedings of the 1996 World Congress on Coastal and Marine Tourism*. Seattle, WA: University of Washington.
- Pearce, D. G. (1992). 'Alternative Tourism: Concepts, Classifications, and Questions', pp. 15-30 in V. L. Smith and W. R. Eadington (eds) *Tourism Alternatives*. Philadelphia, PA: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Poon, A. (1993). *Tourism, Technology and Competitive Strategies*. Oxon: CABI.
- Pubby Vipin (1996). *Shimla Then and Now*, Indus Publishing. pp. 17-34. ISBN 978-81-7387-046-0. Retrieved 16 June 2014
- Swarbrooke, J. and S. Horner (2007). *Consumer Behavior in Tourism*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Teare, R. (1994). *Consumer decision - making*, In R. Teare, J.A. Mazanec, S. Crawford-Welch and S. Calwer (Eds.), *Marketing in Hospitality and Tourism: A consumer focus* (pp. 1-96), Cassell, London.
- Thakur, Hardeep (2008). *Dev Bhoomi-Himachal Pradesh*, JMD Publications, Shimla, p-311
- Torres, R. (2002) 'Cancun's Tourism Development from a Fordist Spectrum of Analysis', *Tourist Studies* 2(1): 87-116.
- Walpole, M. J. and H. J. Goodwin (2000). 'Local Economic Impacts of Dragon Tourism in Indonesia', *Annals of Tourism Research* 27(3): 559-76.
- Weaver, D. B. (2001). 'Ecotourism as Mass Tourism: Contradiction or Reality?' *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly* 42(2): 104-12.
- <http://www2.unwto.org/content/tourism-2012-agenda> assessed on 23rd August, 2013
- <http://eprint.iitd.ac.in/bitstream/handle/12345678/7044/TH-4968.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y> assessed on 1st September, 2013
- <https://www.orfonline.org/research/innovative-sustainable-solutions-can-make-shimla-a-smart-city/> assessed on 1st September, 2013
- <https://www.orfonline.org/research/making-a-smart-city-in-a-fragile-ecosystem-the-case-of-shimla/> assessed on 1st September, 2013
- <https://www.wasd.org.uk/download/green-computing-for-sustainability-a-case-study-of-himachal-pradesh-university-shimla-india/> assessed on 1st September, 2013